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To cite this article: Xuejiao Liu, Shulan Zeng & Milon Potmesil (2025) Quality of life and resilience in individuals with disabilities: a thematic analysis of literature, Cogent Psychology, 12:1, 2564503, DOI: [10.1080/23311908.2025.2564503](https://doi.org/10.1080/23311908.2025.2564503)

To link to this article: <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311908.2025.2564503>

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Published online: 09 Oct 2025.

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Quality of life and resilience in individuals with disabilities: a thematic analysis of literature

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ABSTRACT

This thematic analysis explores the link between resilience and quality of life (QoL) in individuals with disabilities. An electronic search across six databases identified 19 studies, appraised with the Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool. Six themes emerged, highlighting how resilience relates to QoL. Self-efficacy, found in 12 studies, appeared as a key pathway: individuals with greater self-efficacy reported more confidence in managing disability-related challenges, leading to better adjustment and QoL. One study noted that participants who believed in their capacity to overcome barriers also described higher life satisfaction. Overall, resilience and related strategies significantly influence QoL, underscoring the importance of recognizing individuals' capabilities across diagnoses to support their contributions to their own well-being.

IMPACT STATEMENT

This thematic analysis of literature investigated the link between **resilience** and **Quality of Life (QoL)** in individuals with disabilities, identifying key factors influencing this relationship. Based on the analysis of 19 studies, which were evaluated using the Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool (MMAT), six themes were generated that describe how resilience and related processes are discussed in connection with QoL. The results indicate that resilience and related strategies significantly impact QoL outcomes.

The **significance of the work undertaken** lies in extending the theoretical understanding of how resilience and related psychosocial processes shape the quality of life of people with disabilities. The research suggests that self-efficacy and disability acceptance may function as **individual-level resources**, while social and family support serve as **contextual resources**. Self-efficacy, in particular, is often portrayed as a mechanism through which resilience contributes to QoL.

From a practical perspective, the findings emphasize the need for interventions focused on strengthening **self-efficacy**, promoting **disability acceptance**, and building supportive family and community networks. These insights offer important theoretical and practical implications for enhancing the social environments and improving the overall resilience and QoL of individuals with disabilities. Such interventions should be considered in rehabilitation and policy contexts. Recognizing the capabilities of individuals with different diagnoses is essential for supporting their contributions to their QoL.

ARTICLE HISTORY

Received 18 January 2025
Revised 16 September 2025
Accepted 17 September 2025

KEYWORDS

Quality of life; resilience; disability; mixed methods; thematic analysis

SUBJECTS

Inclusion and Special Educational Needs; School Psychology; Education - Social Sciences

Introduction

QoL (QoL) and resilience in the disability community are increasingly essential topics in the social sciences, reflecting broader societal concerns about inclusion and well-being. Understanding and promoting the resilience and QoL of those with disabilities has become urgent as society increasingly emphasizes inclusivity and equality (Tavakoli & Nejad, 2022; Ivić-Hofman et al., 2022). Disability, whether physical, mental, sensory, psychiatric, neurological, or learning, presents unique challenges that significantly impact an individual's daily experience and overall life satisfaction. QoL is described as a multidimensional latent construct by Spieth and Harris (1996), which can be traced back to the World Health Organization's definition of health, which includes mental, physical, and social components. One of the QoL models used in disability is the one developed by Schalock et al. (2010). This model adopts the perspective that QoL is a multifaceted phenomenon comprising eight domains: rights, social inclusion, emotional, physical, and material well-being,

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interpersonal connections, personal development, and self-determination (Helm, 2003). Resilience refers to individuals' capacity to adapt effectively and achieve social, academic, and vocational competence despite adversity and stress (Masten et al., 2008). It involves overcoming challenges and fulfilling age-appropriate developmental milestones (Murray, 2003), viewed as a complex, dynamic process shaped by various internal and external factors (Alvord & Grados, 2005). Understanding how people with disabilities cope with these challenges, build resilience, and maintain QoL is critical to developing effective support systems and policies (Li & Goh, 2011; Persson & Rydén, 2006; Stuntzner & Hartley, 2014). Based on an appreciation of the intricacy of disability life, this research attempts to illuminate these significant facets of human experience.

Despite a growing body of literature investigating the well-being and resilience of people with disabilities, most QoL research has focused on identifying and assessing the general factors influencing QoL, such as socio-economic status, access to healthcare, and social support networks. Researchers have attempted to assess the efficacy of these broad factors without adequately considering the unique and diverse experiences of people with disabilities. Many recent studies (e.g. Crocker et al., 2021; Carrard et al., 2021; Chuang et al., 2023) have shown that the diversity of the disabled population, including differences in disability type, severity, and intersectional identities, significantly impact their QoL and resilience. Much of the research has emphasized factors associated with resilience in people with disabilities, such as individual coping strategies, community support, and access to adaptive technology (Ochs & Roessler, 2001; Ungar, 2006; Ungar et al., 2014). However, these studies have tended to generalize findings to all groups of people with disabilities without considering specific nuances. A relationship exists between an individual's working memory and their ability to cope with everyday challenges, which is critical to building resilience (Siegel & Ryan, 1989). Furthermore, a notable deficiency exists in comprehensive qualitative studies exploring the subjective realities of individuals with disabilities. Most studies on disability have been quantitative, emphasizing statistical correlations rather than rich narrative understandings. Scheffers, Van Vugt, and Moonen (2024) conducted a series of qualitative studies, which suggest that deeper, narrative-based research methods are needed to understand the lived experiences of disabled people. Similarly, Artiles (2013) demonstrated through cross-sectional analyses that multiple identities such as ethnicity, gender, and socio-economic status intersect to shape the resilience and QoL of disabled people. Further research has highlighted the importance of contextual factors in shaping resilience, which cannot be fully captured through quantitative measures alone (Mehta et al., 2008; Phibbs, 2022; Stuntzner et al., 2020; Windle, 2011).

Specifically, this study aimed to explore how adults with disabilities describe resilience and its relationship to quality of life (QoL), and to identify processes that participants perceived as influencing QoL.

Methods

Search strategy

Eligible articles published in journals were identified through the following electronic databases: Proquest Education, Web of Science, ERIC, Education Source, Scopus, and PubMed, using text word search or combinations of (1) for resilience: resilience, mental toughness factor, emotional control factor, life behavior factor, social adaptation factor, academic adjustment factor. (2) for QoL: QoL (QoL); health-related QoL (HRQL or HRQOL); life quality; health status; well-being. In addition, studies on individuals who are typically developing were not retained.

To reduce publication bias, we searched the grey literature, including OpenGrey, ProQuest Dissertations & Theses, selected conference proceedings (searched via Google Scholar), clinical trial registries, and preprint servers. Records from grey sources were screened using the same inclusion criteria as peer-reviewed items. We focused on recent developments in resilience and QoL research, particularly in the post-COVID context, where conceptualizations and service environments changed rapidly.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

For inclusion in the subset of studies for data extraction, the screened studies had to be published in English and address 'QoL' and 'resilience' among individuals with disabilities as the primary goal. Duplicates

Figure 1. Flow chart on different phases of a systematic review.

were removed. Abstracts, editorials, commentaries, reviews, letters, and study protocols were excluded, but they were reviewed for possible references. Abstracts of potential articles were reviewed, and studies that were not focused on people with disabilities, did not provide results on resilience and QoL, and did not look at an association between these constructs were excluded. The flow chart (Figure 1) illustrates the identification and selection procedure. Every study that was included complied fully with ethical guidelines. Full-text articles of the selected abstracts were sought out and reviewed according to the inclusion criteria. To be included, studies used either a quantitative, qualitative, or mixed methods (quantitative and qualitative) methodology. Additionally, reference lists from original papers were reviewed. Google Scholar was used to identify any further relevant articles. All the studies included were in full accordance with ethical guidelines. Two reviewers independently screened titles and abstracts. When the agreement at title/abstract screening was finished, full-text screening agreement was the next step. Disagreements were resolved by discussion and, when necessary, a third reviewer adjudicated. Data extraction was similarly conducted independently by two reviewers with agreement; a random sample of extracted items was double-checked to ensure consistency.

Data extraction and synthesis

In this review, we used reflexive thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006, 2022) as our analytic approach. This method involves familiarisation with the data, coding, generating initial themes, reviewing and refining themes, and naming them. Themes were developed inductively from the data rather than imposed a priori, and our approach prioritized researcher reflexivity and interpretative depth. Inductive vs. deductive coding: Codes and themes were primarily generated inductively from the data (i.e. based on the data). Where existing models of quality of life/resilience were relevant, we reflexively took them into account in developing themes, but we did not force the study results into pre-existing categories. We indicate when a theme reflects a priori analytical categories. The Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic

Reviews and Meta-Analysis (PRISMA) checklist and flowchart were used to verify that all review aspects were considered (Haddaway et al., 2022). This review was not registered in PROSPERO or any other registry; we now state this transparently in line with PRISMA 2020 guidance.

Reflexivity

The research team reflected on their own perspectives and experiences throughout the data collection and analysis stages. Interviewers' backgrounds and potential influences were discussed, and reflexive journaling was used to monitor assumptions and biases. Team discussions were held to ensure transparency and credibility of interpretation.

Quality assessment

The Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool (MMAT, Version 2011) was used to assess study quality (Pluye et al., 2009; Pluye, 2011). It provides four criteria for evaluating both quantitative and qualitative studies. The MMAT demonstrated an intra-class correlation of 0.80 in 2009 pilot testing and has proven to be an effective and practical instrument for appraising mixed methods reviews. Two reviewers assessed the databases independently (i.e. blind to each other) and, following the proposed inclusion criteria, selected the retrieved articles. Later, to eliminate possible publication or selection bias, the results from each reviewer were crossed, and if the first two reviewers did not agree, a third reviewer evaluated the case. The methodological quality included the critical appraisal checklist for cross-sectional studies. The methodological quality criteria of the MMAT are illustrated in Table 1.

Results

Study characteristics

An overview of the methods used in these 19 studies is presented in Table 2: nine were quantitative studies, six were qualitative studies, and four were mixed-methods studies (including cross-sectional studies with interviews and case studies with interviews). In terms of diagnostic criteria, four had persons

Table 1. Mixed methods appraisal tool (MMAT) scores for included studies.

Study	MMAT score
Qualitative studies	
Akoto et al., 2022, New Zealand	***
Angelocci, 2007, USA	****
Bulthuis, 2008, Canada	***
Duma, 2019, South Africa	***
Marwaha & Anand, 2019, USA	**
Wolsey, 2018, USA	****
Quantitative studies	
Álvarez-Aguado et al., 2023, Chile	***
Alriksson-Schmidt et al., 2007, UK	****
Chao, 2017, China (Taiwan)	***
Kim & Park, 2023, South Korea	****
Grenwald-Mayes, 2002, USA	***
Roh, 2023, South Korea	***
Samsari & Soulis, 2019, Greece	***
Alriksson-Schmidt et al., 2007, UK	****
Tavakoli & Nejad, 2022, Iran	***
Zegeye, 2019, Ethiopia	***
Mixed methods studies	
Martins & Moriña, 2022, Portugal	***
Piers & Duquette, 2016, Canada	***
Sifat, 2022, Bangladesh	***
Wilmshurst et al., 2011, USA	***

Note. : Quality rating is calculated based on the Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool (MMAT). For qualitative or quantitative studies, the score equals the number of criteria met divided by four: 25% (*) = one criterion; 50% (**) = two criteria; 75% (***) = three criteria; 100% (****) = all four criteria. For mixed methods studies, the overall score equals the lowest rating among QUAL, QUAN, and MM components: 25% (*) when QUAL = 1 or QUAN = 1 or MM = 0; 50% (**) when QUAL = 2 or QUAN = 2 or MM = 1; 75% (***) when QUAL = 3 or QUAN = 3 or MM = 2; and 100% (****) when QUAL = 4, QUAN = 4, and MM = 3. QUAL=qualitative component score; QUAN=quantitative component score; MM=mixed methods component score.

Table 2. Characteristics of selected studies.

Author, year, country	Focus	Methods	Age mean/SD/range (diagnosis)	Study group (number, gender)	Control group	Instrument/ analysis	Results
Álvarez-Aguado et al., 2023, Chile	Quality of life	Questionnaire	R=35–75 Intellectual disabilities & mental health problems	N=181 Male = 121(66.9%) Female = 60(33.1%)	–	The FUMAT scale	The dimensions of self-determination and personal development obtained the lowest scores. In addition, living in rural settings, receiving regular support, or being a man was associated with a better QoL. Participants were able to maintain their status as university students owing to some support they received at the micro-system, meso-system, and exo-system.
Akoto et al., 2022, New Zealand	Psychosocial Support Services Available	Qualitative semi-structured interviews	R=20–56 Physical disability & visual impairment	N=11 Male = 9 Female = 2	–	Thematic qualitative data analysis	Participants were able to maintain their status as university students owing to some support they received at the micro-system, meso-system, and exo-system.
Airiksson-Schmidt et al., 2007, UK	Quality of Life and Resilience	Questionnaires	M=14.71 SD = 2.14 R=11–18 Mobility disabilities	N=159 Male(52%) Female(52%)	–	Parental report The Quality of Student Life Questionnaire The QL Module of the Behavioral Risk Factor Surveillance System Adolescent Disability Related Life Events Survey The Adolescent Life Events Survey-Revised The Social Skills Rating System Phenomenological analysis	Increased life stress was associated with worse QL. Hypothesized protective variables were used to explain significant variance in more subjective, but not objective, measures of QL beyond covariates and life stress.
Angelocci, 2007, USA	Risk, Resilience, and Success	Semi-structured interview	Junior or senior or have recently graduated (within three years) vision impairments	N=6	–		Risk and protective factors in the context of family, school, and community for successful college students with visual disabilities were identified.
Bulthuis, 2008, Canada	Resilience Factors	Retrospective interviews	R=18–38 learning disabilities	N=8 Male = 6 Female = 2	–	Open-ended questions	This study offered a more personal depiction of the unique contributions their stories made to this study.
Chao, 2017, China (Taiwan)	relationship between self-determination and quality of life	Quantitative	R=22–25 eight different types of disabilities	N=145	–	The Self-Determination Scale for College Students and WHOQOL-BREF	Positive correlations were found between self-determination and quality of life. Subjects' scores on the SDSCS subscales were able to explain between 30.3%–53.2% of the total variance of their scores on the WHOQOL-BREF domains. Many stressors impacted students with disabilities in university residences and these stressors potentially hampered their performance.
Duma, 2019, South Africa	Experiences of Resilience	Semi-structured interviews	Age not stated wheelchair users & dwarfism	N=7 Male = 1 Female = 6	–	Coded themes	Many stressors impacted students with disabilities in university residences and these stressors potentially hampered their performance.

(Continued)

Table 2. Continued.

Author, year, country	Focus	Methods	Age mean/SD/range (diagnosis)	Study group (number, gender)	Control group	Instrument/ analysis	Results
Kim & Park, 2023, South Korea	Structural Relationship among Disability Acceptance, Resilience, and Social Participation	Questionnaire	M = 16.9 Physical disabilities	N = 255 Male = 155 Female = 100	-	Exploratory Factor Analysis Confirmatory Factor Analysis Cronbach's Alpha test correlation analysis and Structural Equation Modelling	Disability acceptance affected resilience and social participation, but the influence that disability acceptance had on social participation was not significant.
Martins & Moríña, 2022, Portugal	Resilience Factors	Qualitative	R = 18–20 Physical disability & hearing impairment	N = 4	-	Semi-Structured Interview Measuring State and Child Resilience Inventory Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale Positive Affect Negative Affectivity Scale Closed coding	Resilience, self-esteem, family support, subjective well-being, and psychological well-being are protective factors that contribute to good adaptation and better inclusion in higher education.
Marwaha & Anand, 2019, USA	Happiness, Meaning in life, Hope and Resilience	Open-ended interview	R = 18–25 Visual Impairment	N = 38 Male = 9 Female = 29	N = 26 Male = 11 Female = 15		Irrespective of disability, certain themes emerged that were common across the four categories of participants: happiness, meaning in life, hope, and resilience.
Grenwald-Mayes, 2002, USA	Relationship between current quality of life and family of origin dynamics	Questionnaire	M = 24.32 (the study group) M = 27.63 (the control group) ADHD	N = 37 Male = 18 (48.6%) Female = 19 (51.4%)	N = 59 Male = 22 (37.3%) Female = 37 (62.7%)	Background information questionnaire Quality of Life Questionnaire Family Environment Scale The Family Adaptation and Cohesion Scale II	In comparison to the control group, the ADHD group reported lower quality of life. The ADHD and non-ADHD groups did not differ significantly in reported family-of-origin relationship dynamics.
Piers & Duquette, 2016, Canada	Academic and Mental Health Resilience	Retrospective, Case Study	R = 20–32 learning disabilities	N = 13	-	Individual semi-structured in-depth interviews	The participants identified many interactions between the students and their parents, teachers, and peers that helped shape and develop the capacities they needed to negotiate for the support and resources that sustained their well-being.
Roh, 2023, South Korea	The Effect of Resilience and Self-Efficacy	Quantitative	Age not stated diagnosis not reported	N = 238 Male = 96(40.3%) Female = 142(59.7%)	-	The Korean Resilience Quotient The Career Decision-Making Self-Efficacy Scale Short Form The Career Preparation Behavior Scale The Career Decision-Making Autonomous Scale	Resilience, self-efficacy, and intrinsic motivation had a significant positive correlation with career preparation behavior.
Samsari & Soulis, 2019, Greece	Problem Solving and Resilience Self-Efficacy	Questionnaire(self-report)	R = 15- about 50 Physical disability	N = 150 Male = 76 Female = 74	N = 150 Male = 76 Female = 74	Self-Efficacy Expectations Scale Subjective Happiness Scale quantitative data analysis	Positive correlations among problem-solving self-efficacy, resilience self-efficacy, and subjective well-being, while statistically significant differences were found in the level of the above factors between participants with and without disability.
Sifat, 2022, Bangladesh	Mental Resilience and Quality Of Life	Cross-sectional study	M = 46.09 SD = 15.40 diagnosis not reported	N = 143	-	Standard structured questionnaire having socio-demographic SF 36 questionnaire The 'Brief Resilience Scale'	Prevalence of the level of mental resilience was low = 70.6%, normal = 19.6% & high = 9.8%. A statistically significant association was also found between Mental Resilience & some socio-demographic information.

(Continued)

Table 2. Continued.

Author, year, country	Focus	Methods	Age mean/SD/range (diagnosis)	Study group (number, gender)	Control group	Instrument/ analysis	Results
Tavakoli & Nejad, 2022, Iran	The Relationship between Perceived Social Support and Psychological Resilience	Questionnaires	R = 15–65 Physical disabilities	N = 100	–	The Social Support Appraisals Scale Klohn Ego Resilience Scale World Health Organization Quality of Life-BRIEF	There is a positive relationship between perceived social support and quality of life in people with physical disabilities. The higher the social support, the higher the quality of life, as well as between psychological resilience and quality.
Wolsey, 2018, USA	resiliency and adaptability in the experiences	Case study	R = 20–40 M = 29 DeafBlind	N = 5	–	Grounded theory	Highlighted the importance of 'access to communication and information' for DeafBlind students.
Wilmshurst et al., 2011, USA	Resilience and Well-being	Structured interview	R = 18–20 ADHD	N = 17 Male = 10 (58.8%) Female = 7 (41.2%)	N = 19 Male = 6 Female = 13	Structured interview, Adult ADHD Rating Scales Conners' Continuous Performance Test II Tennessee Self-Concept Scale Scales of Psychological Well-Being	Between group differences were significant for the CAARS and CPT-II, but not total self-concept (TSC) or global PWB. The strongest predictors for TSC were environmental mastery (PWB) for the ADHD group and positive relations with others (PWB) for the controls.
Zegeye, 2019, Ethiopia	the status of resilience	Survey	R = 13–19 visual disability	N = 69 Male = 32 Female = 28	–	Connor-Davidson Resilience Scale	The results revealed a lower level of resilience. Gender, time of onset of blindness, parental education, and family income influence resilience.

with physical disabilities, three with visual disability, two studies each with learning disabilities and attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD), one study each with individuals with intellectual disabilities with mental health problems, mobility disabilities, Deafblind, physical disability with visual impairment or hearing impairment, combined disabilities, and two studies did not report diagnosis types. The gender of males was generally more represented than females in the studies where numbers were reported, except for four studies (Duma, 2019; Grenwald-Mayes, 2002; Marwaha & Anand, 2019; Roh, 2023). The main findings are also summarized in Table 2. Four studies adopted a study group and control group design, and one used a qualitative randomized control. Another ten studies measured the association between resilience and QoL using standardized tools to assess both constructs. These studies used different instruments to measure resilience and QoL. They included generic and disease-specific QoL measures, evaluating their QoL using four domains, including Physical Health, Psychological, Social Relationships, and Environment (Álvarez-Aguado et al., 2023; Angelocci, 2007; Chao, 2017; Grenwald-Mayes, 2002; Martins & Moriña, 2022; Roh, 2023; Samsari & Soulis, 2019; Sifat, 2022; Tavakoli & Nejad, 2022; Wilmshurst et al., 2011; Zegeye, 2019).

Resilience and QoL were often measured through self-report or parent-report questionnaires and with objective physical activity measures such as accelerometry. These studies found a positive relationship between higher resilience scores and enhanced QoL. One of these studies (Tavakoli & Nejad, 2022) found that a higher level of social support is positively associated with an enhanced QoL, alongside a significant correlation between psychological resilience and overall QoL. All six qualitative studies indicated that protective factors contribute to a good adaptation and better inclusion and access to communication and information, as well as emphasizing a positive relationship between perceived social support and QoL in people with physical disabilities (Akoto et al., 2022; Angelocci, 2007; Bulthuis, 2008; Duma, 2019; Marwaha & Anand, 2019; Wolsey, 2018). Similarly, many stressors impacted students with disabilities in university residences, and these stressors potentially hampered their performance.

Theme 1: Resilience and QoL

Resilience is essential to the QoL of people with disabilities (Alriksson-Schmidt et al., 2007). Several studies remarked that mental toughness was positively associated with QoL, while self-efficacy, resilience, and intrinsic motivation were also strongly associated with career preparation behaviors (Chao, 2017; Samsari & Soulis, 2019). Specifically, one study reported a positive correlation between resilience, self-efficacy, intrinsic motivation, and career preparation behavior (Roh, 2023). A study conducted by Sifat (2022) on mental resilience and QoL for people with disability aimed during the COVID-19 pandemic showed that disability can negatively decrease mental resilience and QoL. Another study has established that numerous stressors significantly affect students with disabilities in university residences, potentially hindering their academic performance (Duma, 2019). For example, disability affects physical health problems, emotional health problems, social activities, energy and emotions, and the general health of this group. Therefore, these findings indicate that a higher level of resilience contributed to QoL.

Theme 2: Self-determination and QoL

There is growing mindfulness in the fields of disability services, rehabilitation, education, and psychology, which necessitates promoting self-determination for people with disabilities (M Wehmeyer & Schwartz, 1998). Recent studies (e.g. Álvarez-Aguado et al., 2023; Chao, 2017) have shown that self-determination and personal development significantly impact individuals' QoL, including their performance in different social situations. Furthermore, the result revealed that college students with disabilities showed more significant levels of life quality the more self-determination they possessed (Chao, 2017). Therefore, as a component of QoL, self-determination is essential to improving the mental health and overall well-being of people with disabilities.

Theme3: self-efficacy, resilience, and psychological adaptation

Self-efficacy is a determining factor of the psychological adaptation of a person with a disability (Cunningham et al., 1991). According to Bandura (1999), self-efficacy is the motivational orientation that

supports individuals in achieving self-regulation and encourages them when encountering challenges. In several reports, self-efficacy and resilience are essential psychological resources that positively impact the psychological adjustment and subjective well-being of individuals with disabilities (Kim & Park, 2023; Roh, 2023; Samsari & Soulis, 2019). In general, self-efficacy is positively correlated with the level of resilience; that is, high self-efficacy is associated with higher levels of resilience. For example, people with disabilities may be prevented from experiencing success in a variety of areas of everyday life (such as employment, leisure, and education), which could lead to a decrease in self-confidence relative to those without disabilities. Researchers attempted to evaluate the impact of resilience on students with learning disabilities, including ways of facing adversity and the role of family support (Bulthuis, 2008). Another study has explored the relationships between resilience, self-efficacy, and intrinsic motivation, and career preparation behaviors showed a significant positive correlation with career preparation behaviors (Roh, 2023). Regarding psychological adaptation, emotional stability is crucial for student success, especially for those with disabilities who face additional challenges like marginalization and discrimination (Akoto et al., 2022). Overall, data from several sources have identified a positive correlation between self-efficacy, resilience, and psychological adaptation. It was further found that self-efficacy significantly predicted the subjective well-being of people with disabilities.

Theme 4: Disability acceptance, resilience, and social participation

Disability acceptance is an indispensable factor for individuals with disabilities to lead fulfilling lives as members of society since it recognizes their value and does not negatively influence their self-evaluation (Livneh, 2001). Social participation refers to actively participating in various activities by establishing a social network in the environment surrounding an individual. Several lines of evidence suggest that disability acceptance influences individual resilience and social participation (Kim & Park, 2023; Tavakoli & Nejad, 2022). However, a relatively small body of literature is concerned with disability acceptance. Some QoL variables include adaptability to the disability of their experiences (Piers & Duquette, 2016; Wolsey, 2018). Individuals with disabilities can benefit from supportive relationships, positive social participation, and strong family dynamics to increase their resilience.

Theme 5: Impact of family, school, and social support on disability

Social support constituted a pivotal component of overall QoL. Social support was collectively perceived as positive for the QoL of disability (Tavakoli & Nejad, 2022). One study highlighted life stress, resources, and social support associated with the QoL of adolescents with mobility limitations (Alriksson-Schmidt et al., 2007). It is noted that perceived social support positively correlates with the QoL and mental health of people with physical disabilities (Akoto et al., 2022; Tavakoli & Nejad, 2022). The findings of the study point to the fact that students with disabilities face a variety of challenges in the college environment, but through social support and interactions with family, faculty, and peers, they can maintain their identity as college students and achieve academic success (Akoto et al., 2022; Duma, 2019; Piers & Duquette, 2016). Another study reported that risk and protective factors in family, school, and community environments were analyzed, as well as the importance of personal qualities in coping with disability (Angelocci, 2007). This indicates that personal empowerment and social support are critical to student development and well-being (Piers & Duquette, 2016).

Theme 6: Inconsistency of research results on the QoL of disabilities

Three out of the four comparative studies of the QoL of disability groups in both study and control groups explored the impact of ADHD on the lives of college students (Grenwald-Mayes, 2002; Samsari & Soulis, 2019; Wilmshurst et al., 2011). Samsari and Soulis (2019) focus on the relationship between self-efficacy and subjective well-being in a specific population of people with and without physical disabilities in Greece. Wilmshurst et al. (2011) and Grenwald-Mayes (2002) examine the impact of ADHD on the self-conception, mental health, and QoL of college students and compare them to their peers without ADHD.

Regarding the findings, it has been demonstrated that people with physical disabilities scored lower on problem-solving self-efficacy, resilience self-efficacy, and subjective well-being compared to people

without physical disabilities (Samsari & Soulis, 2019). Furthermore, they identified that the need for companionship and satisfaction with transportation autonomy are significant factors influencing self-efficacy and subjective well-being among individuals with physical disabilities. Moreover, Wilmshurst et al. (2011) stated that despite significant differences in ADHD indicators, there were no significant differences in overall self-concept or overall psychological well-being between college students with ADHD and their non-ADHD peers. However, specific findings indicated that the overall self-concept of students with ADHD was predicted by environmental mastery, whereas in the control group, having positive relationships with others was a significant predictor of overall self-concept. Similarly, Grenwald-Mayes (2002) found that the ADHD group reported a lower QoL compared to the non-ADHD group but reported no significant differences in family-of-origin relationship dynamics. In summary, family relationship dynamics were a strong predictor of the current overall QoL in the ADHD group but were less influential in the non-ADHD group.

Discussion

First, it has been suggested that mental resilience positively correlates with QoL, while self-efficacy and resilience are strongly associated with career preparation (Chao, 2017; Roh, 2023; Samsari & Soulis, 2019). This is consistent with findings in the existing literature (Brace et al., 2020), emphasizing the positive impact of mental toughness and self-efficacy on individuals. Therefore, increasing mental toughness and self-efficacy may contribute to the QoL and career preparation of students with disabilities.

Vocational rehabilitation is an essential component of career preparation for individuals with intellectual disabilities (Reims & Tisch, 2022). However, it has been argued that students with disabilities lag significantly behind in vocational maturity, and in particular, special education students scored significantly lower than general education students in the areas of vocational decision-making self-efficacy, vocational outcome expectations, vocational exploration intentions, and vocational identity (Och and Roessler, 2001). Studies indicated that many students with disabilities are unable to find suitable jobs or sustain employment due to a lack of social and interpersonal skills (Wolfe et al., 1998). Traditionally, many studies have identified the need for supported employment for the disability community (Stevens & Martin, 1999). Therefore, interventions targeted at enhancing students' self-efficacy, in addition to currently implemented career training programs, are critical to their career readiness development.

According to Linn (1996), self-efficacy is an unambiguous factor of career readiness. Career decision-making, performance, perseverance, and employment outcomes are closely linked to self-efficacy for individuals with and without disabilities (Betz & Hackett, 1981; Lent et al., 1986). Och and Roessler (2001) present that self-efficacy may help individuals with intellectual disabilities develop their level of career choice and employment readiness. Studies have shown an association between career readiness behaviors and self-efficacy (Roh, 2023); that is, the higher the level of intrinsic motivation, the greater the control of the indirect effect. This research is consistent with previous findings suggesting that self-efficacy is strongly related to career readiness (Alfaiz et al., 2021; Lent et al., 1986; Mahmud et al., 2022).

Therefore, vocational rehabilitation programs are essential for equipping individuals with intellectual disabilities with the information, skills, and self-confidence necessary to enter the labor market. For example, job skills training, developing work habits, and increasing self-efficacy should be included (Chithrangathan, 2022). In other words, teaching social skills through storytelling, videos, role-playing, and involving students in transition planning and career decision-making can increase their self-efficacy (Blalock, 1996). Hall (2003) demonstrated that it would be beneficial if counselors worked with parents to guide their children through career exploration and job search. In addition, through career talks, work visits, and internships, students with intellectual disabilities can better understand the roles and requirements of different careers and be prepared for employment.

Second, this study identified the challenges that students with disabilities face in the college environment and the factors that contribute to their success. It was discovered that the support of microsystems (family), mesosystems (peer support), and ecosystems (financial, institutional, psychological, and academic support) all contribute to the ability of students with disabilities to adapt on college campuses (Akoto et al., 2022; Duma, 2019; Piers & Duquette, 2016). This illustrates the crucial role of social support in helping students with impairments achieve success. Therefore, social support has conclusively increased

the overall QoL and well-being of individuals with disabilities (Braithwaite et al., 1999; Kim et al., 2021; Lombardi et al., 2016).

Third, disability acceptance is related to resilience, supporting the results from the prior researchers Rea-Amaya et al. (2017), who mentioned that positively oriented people with disabilities are more able to make use of their material and human resources than negatively oriented people, and they can effectively maintain self-control under pressure. This suggests that a person's resilience is impacted by their activity level through disability acceptance (Migerode et al., 2012). Therefore, as described by Dymecka et al. (2021) and Yehene et al. (2020) can be inferred from the results of this study, since the response to disability is closely related to a lower level of self-efficacy and psychological adaptation, a program to improve disability acceptance for individuals with disabilities should be offered from an integrated perspective of targeted psychological support services, and thereby strengthening the resilience ability of people with disabilities.

Furthermore, the resilience of individuals with disabilities significantly impacts social participation, confirming the study of Silverman et al. (2015) that resilience serves as a protective factor with beneficial effects on the social functioning of individuals with disabilities. According to Kim and Park (2023), resilience directly impacted social participation, while societal acceptance of disabilities was indirectly impacted by resilience. The result supported previous studies (Migerode et al., 2012; Runswick-Cole & Goodley, 2013; Wright & Masten, 2005) investigating resilience's moderating role in stressful circumstances, including disability acceptance. Additionally, this result is consistent with Armstrong et al. (2005), who stated that resilience affects social participation through self-effective coping strategies for internal and external stress. Therefore, resilience as recovery elasticity can be deduced to have the impact of minimizing risk variables and greatly enhancing the interacting effects of environmental, familial, and personal protection factors (Kim & Park, 2023). However, as demonstrated by prior research and the findings of this study, resilience can be enhanced to provide sufficient compensation. In other words, it can mitigate and moderate an individual's positive or negative mental situation, directly or indirectly impacting their overall social participation (Wright & Masten, 2005). In conclusion, supportive connections with others, family functioning, and the social environment can all help people with disabilities become more resilient (Barnhart et al., 2022). Therefore, the psychological mechanism of resilience should be actively utilized to promote future participation by people with disabilities, which includes positive, supportive connections and can be promoted by increasing participation in various social activities (Shandra, 2022).

In addition, we discovered that a person's QoL is significantly impacted by their capacity for self-determination and personal development (Álvarez-Aguado et al., 2023; Marwaha & Anand, 2019), which emphasized that personal development and autonomy could contribute to the individual's well-being and life satisfaction. Therefore, educating and supporting an individual's autonomy and personal development concerning developmental dynamics helps to improve their QoL (Hardiana & Dewi, 2023).

Moreover, the study showed that there was a substantial difference in subjective well-being according to the gender of participants with disabilities. Women had a lower subjective well-being than men (Samsari & Soulis, 2019). In other words, being a man was associated with a better QoL (Álvarez-Aguado et al., 2023).

Lastly, the disparities in outcomes among the three comparative studies were analyzed as follows: In terms of research focus, the study conducted by Samsari and Soulis (2019) highlighted the relationship between self-efficacy and subjective well-being, particularly among Greek populations with and without physical disabilities. In contrast, Wilmshurst et al. (2011) and Grenwald-Mayes (2002) focused on revealing the impact of ADHD on college students' self-concept, mental health, and QoL through comparisons with peers without ADHD. Regarding fields of study, Samsari and Soulis (2019) diverged by focusing on physical disabilities, whereas the other two studies exclusively addressed ADHD. Cultural differences could have affected the results of the research by Samsari and Soulis (2019), Wilmshurst et al. (2011), and Grenwald-Mayes (2002), as the former was carried out in Greece and the latter two in the United States.

Other factors that could contribute to inconsistent findings include: 1) Sample Characteristics, such as age, gender, and socioeconomic status, may have differed across the three studies, which may have affected the results. 2) Measurement Methods: Methods used to measure self-efficacy, subjective well-being, self-concept, and QoL may have differed across the three studies, affecting comparisons of the results. 3) Variables of the Study: There were differences between the variables explored in the three

studies. Samsari and Soulis (2019) explored dimensions including self-efficacy, resilience, and subjective well-being, and Wilmshurst et al. (2011) determined components of psychological well-being and self-concept. In addition, Grenwald-Mayes (2002) explored the relationship dynamics among the QoL, family of origin relationship dynamics, and the presence of attention deficit. Thus, variations among variables may lead to discrepancies when comparing research findings.

Limitations

Thematic analysis is widely used in qualitative research, especially in literature. However, it has limitations that must be considered before it can be transferred to authorial practice (Naeem et al., 2023).

The unevenness of the sample in the included studies: male participants predominated significantly over female participants; for example, 66.9 percent of the N=181 sample were male, and only 33.1 percent were female. This imbalance may lead to the under-representation of research findings by gender, thereby restricting a comprehensive understanding of the distinctions between gender groups.

Limitations of the sample: The sample in the included studies may not fully represent the entire target population. Since previous research did not involve all disability types in the investigation of QoL, the study's thematic analyses did not encompass all disability categories. Specifically, physical, visual, hearing, learning disabilities and autism spectrum disorders were more prevalent in the university student study group, while intellectual disabilities were underrepresented. For example, Piers and Duquette (2016) studied academic and mental health resilience of physical disability and hearing impairment in 18–20-year-olds through retrospective and case studies. Wolsey (2018) analyzed resiliency and adaptability in the experiences of the Deaf-Blind aged 20–40. Tavakoli and Nejad (2022) used questionnaires to determine the relationship between perceived social support and psychological resilience with physical disabilities aged 15–65. This study has shown a positive relationship between perceived social support and QoL in people with physical disabilities. In another study on intellectual disabilities and mental health problems, Álvarez-Aguado et al. (2023) investigated the QoL among individuals aged 35–75 years, excluding university students, reflecting the lower prevalence of intellectual disabilities in this demographic.

The homogeneity of the research methodology: Most studies on QoL and resilience used questionnaires and semi-structured methods, which improve the quantitative and qualitative data but ignore other possible data collection methods, such as observation or experimentation. As a result, it may not provide a comprehensive picture of the study group.

Research designs used cross-sectional studies: trends and dynamics over time could not be captured, and longer-term follow-up studies may be more revealing of the adjustment processes and changes in the university environment for students with disabilities.

Self-reporting bias: Most questionnaires used in the study were based on self-reporting, which may have been influenced by participants' subjective biases or memory biases, leading to distortion of the data.

Theoretical and practical implications

Our findings extend the theoretical understanding of how resilience and related psychosocial processes shape the quality of life of people with disabilities. They suggest that resilience, self-efficacy, and acceptance may function as individual-level resources, while social and family support serve as contextual resources. These insights generate hypotheses for future quantitative and mixed-method studies.

Practically, the findings highlight the importance of interventions that enhance self-efficacy, promote acceptance of disability, and build family and community support networks. Such interventions may improve quality of life and should be considered in rehabilitation and policy contexts. However, longitudinal and experimental work is needed to verify causality and effectiveness.

Conclusion

This study explored the factors influencing the level of resilience and the QoL of the disability community by thematically analyzing 19 included papers using the PRISMA literature assessment method. Significant findings related to QoL, psychological resilience, self-efficacy, social support, and personal development of students with disabilities were identified.

The findings highlight the importance of social support for students with disabilities and the positive impact of mental toughness and self-efficacy on their adjustment and success. These findings offer theoretical and practical insights for enhancing the social environments of disability groups and improving resilience and overall QoL.

Despite the meaningful findings of the study, it is essential to realize some limitations. For example, the unbalanced nature of the sample and the research methodology's homogeneity may limit the findings' generalisability and interpretability.

Future research could further explore the factors that contribute to the adaptability and achievement of students with disabilities in the university environment, employ more diverse methods of literature assessment to address the limitations in the current thematic analysis, and provide better support and services for students with disabilities.

Declarations of authors

- The authors have no relevant financial or non-financial interests to disclose.
- The authors have no competing interests to declare relevant to this article's content.
- All authors certify that they have no affiliations with or involvement in any organization or entity with any financial or non-financial interest in the subject matter or materials discussed in this manuscript.
- The authors have no financial or proprietary interests in any material discussed in this article.

Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the author(s).

The project framework

This review was completed within the framework of the scientific projects of the Institute of Special Education and the Center for Evidence-Based Education and Art Therapy, Faculty of Education, Palacký University in Olomouc, Palacký University in Olomouc project IGA_PdF_2024_014 and US-WEINOE 15-1213-001-1-10-06. ReDiKid Project: Resilient Child in the Digital World, reg. no. CZ.02.01.01/00/23_025/0008686, co-financed by the EU.

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Data availability statement

The article is a review, and no data were used for processing. Therefore, Data Availability is not applied.

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